

Challenges on the numerical prediction of slamming loads on LNG tank insulation panels

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Abstract

The load assessment in water impacts problems involving complex geometries is generally a quite challenging task for numerical solvers. Indeed, the occurrence of large free-surface deformation, air cushioning and possible compressibility effects strain the standard Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes to their limits. In the present work, an enhanced Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) model is adopted to evaluate the pressures acting on the surface of smooth and corrugated panels impacting water and the numerical outcomes are compared to experimental data and analytical solutions. Specifically, the water entry of a flat panel at 4° is firstly studied in order to highlight the main critical aspects underlying the numerical solution of water impacts with small deadrise angles. Then, the water impact of a Mark III type panel (a corrugated insulation panel) adopted in LNG tanks is considered. Experimental data involving wet drop tests of both flat and corrugated panels have been performed and the pressures during the impact have been measured at several points along the panel surface. Complex features of the flow, such as 3D effects and air-cushioning, have been addressed by a developing the numerical study in steps of increasing complexity.

Key words: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics; Water impact; Slamming; air-cushion effects; Trapped gas cavity; LNG tank;

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Fig. 1. Left: A membrane type LNG carrier. Right: Inside view of the Cargo Containment System (CCS) of a LNG carrier, the surface of the tank is covered by Mark III corrugation panels.

1 Introduction

In recent years the consumption of the Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) fuel has largely increased due to the commitment of nations to reduce noxious emissions of standard fuels, notably NO_x and SO_x oxide. In order to reduce the transportation cost as well as to meet the increased demand of LNG, designers have considered larger LNG carriers. These vessels are designed and constructed for safe transportation of natural gas at cryogenic temperatures. Storage and transportation of LNG are critical issues in the design and safety aspects of LNG carrier. In particular, the Cargo Containment System (CCS), which is responsible for keeping the liquid at low temperature (-165°C), is a key component. The CCS is a composite structure of metal membrane, polyurethane foam and plywood laminated insulator and its strength can be characterized as the maximum load that the system can sustain before it fails. The loads acting on the insulation system are due to the sloshing motion of the liquid in the LNG tank and are typically the result of an impact flow dynamics, which is generally characterized by an impulsive loading processes. The design of CCS should adequately take into account such load features to evaluate the strength and failure mode of the insulation system. This applies a fortiori in the contemporary shipping context, in which the LNG tank is not barely filled or empty (as it was the case in the past). Indeed, as remarked in [19], due to the changed market demand, nowadays any filling level is allowed, which introduces higher risks related to sloshing fluid motions.

Recently, deformations of primary corrugation membrane (Mark III type, see right plot of figure 1) adopted in LNG tanks have been reported (see, e.g.,[4]). As a consequence, the importance of the load assessment on corrugated insulation panels has become increasingly relevant (see, e.g., [6, 5]). The present investigation is dedicated to the numerical simulation of wet drop tests of a Mark-III insulation panel using the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method and to the validation of the numerical results against experimental data. The wet drop test consists in the water entry of the

panel with a specific configuration and at a fixed velocity. This kind of test case can be seen as analogous to the problem of a fluid wedge impacting a vertical wall (see, e.g., [32]) and can give useful insights for the more complex problem of a wave impacting a wall composed by Mark III panels. With respect to the latter, in the wet drop test it is simpler to control and reproduce (also numerically) the impact conditions, allowing for a detailed comparison between physical model and numerical output. Because of the small deadrise angle, the numerical simulation of such an impact is quite demanding and requires suitable models. Among the available solvers, the SPH method has been selected, being accurate and robust in treating violent free-surface flows. A brief description of the method is given in section 3. In order to address the capability of such a solver, a test using a flat plate is used in a preliminary test. Indeed, for such a simple geometry solutions using potential theory are available (being aware of the fact that these solutions are referred to a symmetrical flow, see e.g. [33, 28, 8]) and, furthermore, experimental data are also available. For the chosen impact angle the air phase can be neglected, therefore allowing for a simple comparison between experimental and numerical outcomes. The analytical references and the experimental data allows the proper establishment of the time-space discretization for the other test-cases investigated (see section 4). A critical discussion on the comparison between analytical solution, numerical results and experiments will be given by focusing the most relevant challenges of the numerical simulation of water impact.

Regarding the actual focus of the present work, for the Mark-III insulation panel the entrapping of the gaseous phase by the liquid one can play a significant role on the time-space distributions of the local loads. Because of the square geometry, formed by the corrugation stencil, 3D effects can also be relevant, indeed the water impact jets can be deflected and focused on specific zones of the panel. The effect of the surface tension can be also important in the bubble-flow formation as a result of the gas trapped during the impact stages. Because of the above considerations, numerical simulation of the water impact against Mark-III insulation panel requires two-phase 3D simulations with an accurate surface-tension model. To our knowledge this kind of numerical investigation is not yet available in the literature, even in the most recent works, mainly because of the high computation costs involved.

In a recent paper by [19] the initial stage of the impact of the Mark-III panel is studied in 2D with null deadrise angle by means of a Wagner approach. In that study also the air compressibility and the structure elasticity are taken into account. Conversely, in the present work a dead-rise angle equal to 4° is considered and, hence, the role of the air can not be a priori assessed. Therefore, in order to tackle the problem in steps with increasing complexity, the analysis has been subdivided in three sets of simulations:

- i) 2D single-phase simulations
- ii) 3D single-phase simulations
- iii) 2D two-phase simulations

Due to these three steps, it is possible separate the role of 3D effects and the air cushion phenomena. Future perspectives and conclusions will wrap-up the paper.

2 Experimental Set-up

Wet drop tests of the Mark-III insulation panel were performed in the Slamming Research Lab. at Pusan National University. The maximum drop height tested was 3.8 m. The incident angles were 4, and 6 degrees. In the present work only the first condition has been considered, it being the most critical.

The dimensions of the test specimens were 640x520 mm (LxB). The specimens used in the drop test were: a real Mark III corrugation membrane (steel SUS304L, of thickness 1.2 mm), a rigid flat plate (steel thickness 20 mm, hereinafter referred as the flat panel) and a rigid Mark III corrugated panel (steel, thickness 20 mm).

Fig. 2. Test specimen and setup for the drop test experiment.

Fig. 3. Flat (left) and corrugated (right) panels used in the drop tests. The holes visible in both the pictures indicates the location of the pressure sensors.

The flat plate was tested in order to compare the pressure distribution measurements with reference data available in the literature. The real corrugated membrane was tested to find the relation between the drop height and the deformation of the corrugation, facilitating the analysis of the buckling strength of the membrane. However, in the present work the hydroelastic problem is not considered and we focus our investigation only on the rigid panels in order to study the pressure distributions developed during the water entry.

The pressure sensors used were ICP type sensors whose maximum capacity is 70 bar. The size of the pressure gauge is 6.3 mm. The sampling rate of the data acquisition was up to 100 kHz which is expected to be high enough to capture the time histories of the pressure impacts, even for the small dead-rise angles considered here (see e.g., [29, 18]).

Figure 2 shows a picture of the drop test facility used in the Slamming Research Lab of Pusan National University; in figure 3 pictures of the rigid panels are shown. The total weight of the support, the wedge and the panels is about 1500 kg, which guarantees that during the impact stages the deceleration of the wedge is negligible (as confirmed by the time history of the wedge displacement, which was measured using accelerometers). This allowed numerical simulations imposing a constant water entry velocity, thus avoiding the possibility of errors due to changing body velocity during the drop test.

As noted in [33], the effects of changes in velocity are not always considered in many of the works presented in the literature. In [33], the authors also remark on the importance of the size of the pressure gauges; indeed as discussed in the following section, this needs to be taken in to account when small deadrise angles are considered.

3 The Riemann-ALE Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics model

In the present work the Riemann-based solver described in [26] is adopted. In that work Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formalism is used allowing for maintaining a regular particle spatial distribution and smooth pressure fields while preserving the whole scheme conservation and consistency of the classical SPH scheme.

Both compressible and incompressible formulations of SPH can be found in the literature. We focus here in its compressible form, addressing weakly-compressible fluids. Therefore, the continuity equation is used together with the Euler equation:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \\ \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where D/Dt represents the Lagrangian derivative, while \mathbf{r} , \mathbf{u} , p and ρ are, respectively, the position of a generic material point, its velocity, pressure and density; and \mathbf{g} represents gravitational acceleration. The system (1) is written in a Lagrangian form, which represents one of the main attractions of the SPH method. Since the Reynolds number of the flow is quite high and only the impact stage is simulated (short time-range regime) viscous effects can be considered negligible. Moreover, the fluid is assumed to be barotropic and, therefore, the following functional dependence between ρ and p is adopted:

$$p(\rho) = \frac{c_0^2 \rho_0}{\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right] + p_0, \quad (2)$$

where ρ_0 and p_0 are constant, c_0 is the speed of sound, and γ is a dimensionless parameter greater than 1 (in all of the following examples $\gamma = 7$ is used).

In the SPH method, the speed of sound c_0 is chosen much lower than the real one, but much higher than the reference velocity, U_{ref} , to satisfy the weakly-compressible assumption. When considering violent free-surface flows, the proper identification of the reference velocity U_{ref} is crucial, as is discussed in the following sections. Considering the Mach number $\text{Ma} = U_{ref}/c_0$, the constraint $\text{Ma} < 0.1$ is taken into account to make compressibility effects negligible. Additionally, during violent impact events (i.e., flat impacts) the acoustic pressure $p = \rho u c_0$ can be reached, and in this case the pressure

peak intensity becomes proportional to $1/\text{Ma}$. On the other hand, in such a condition an incompressible constraint can induce singularities on the pressure field (see [22] for a discussion on the difference between these two models in impact situations). This is linked to the fact that for this kind of impacts the presence of the air phase is generally crucial and the single-phase approach can lead to incorrect pressure evaluations under the incompressible/weakly-compressible hypothesis (for a deeper discussion see also [24]). Being aware of these limits for a single-phase model, the results obtained in this paper have been produced considering a possible Mach dependency.

The SPH model is based on the interpolation of a generic flow field f through a convolution integral with a kernel function W over its compact support Ω :

$$\langle f \rangle(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{r}') W(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}; h) dV' \quad (3)$$

The fluid domain is discretized into a finite number of particles representing elementary fluid volumes, each with its own local mass m_i and other physical properties. At the discrete level a generic field f evaluated at the position \mathbf{r}_i of the i -th particle is approximated through a convolution sum. Equation (3) thus becomes:

$$\langle f \rangle(\mathbf{r}_i) = \sum_j f(\mathbf{r}_j) W(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j; h) V_j \quad (4)$$

where V_j is the volume of the j -th particle. Hence any function or its gradient can be interpolated in total absence of connectivity.

The use of the Riemann-based solver leads to an increased stability and robustness of the scheme with respect to standard SPH schemes. The formalism proposed by [30], which is inspired by compressible Finite Volume techniques, is adopted. For each pair of particle-to-particle interactions (i, j) , a Riemann problem is solved in the direction (i, j) for Tait's equation of state, providing a solution for the flux that is then convolved using the kernel gradient in order to solve for the expected flux divergence. Thanks to the introduction of Riemann-solvers the fluxes between particles are upwind oriented and the resulting scheme is characterized by good stability properties.

The discrete Euler equations are written as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{D\mathbf{r}_i}{Dt} = \mathbf{v}_{0i}, \\ \frac{DV_i}{Dt} = V_i \sum_j (\mathbf{v}_{0j} - \mathbf{v}_{0i}) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{D(V_i \rho_i)}{Dt} = -V_i \sum_j 2\rho_E (\mathbf{v}_E - \mathbf{v}_0(\mathbf{r}_{ij})) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{D(V_i \rho_i \mathbf{v}_i)}{Dt} = -V_i \sum_j 2[\rho_E \mathbf{v}_E \otimes (\mathbf{v}_E - \mathbf{v}_0(\mathbf{r}_{ij})) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \quad - V_i \sum_j 2P_E \mathbf{I} \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \omega_i \rho_i \mathbf{g} \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

where ρ_E , P_E and \mathbf{v}_E are the solutions of the Riemann problem at the interface $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = (\mathbf{r}_i + \mathbf{r}_j)/2$, between particles i and j . The particle transport velocity v_0 is obtained as the summation of the particle velocity plus a small perturbation which helps preserving a regular particle distribution (details about the adopted model can be found in [26]).

The two-phase model is based on the work by Leduc et al. [21] where an approximate Riemann solver without mass fluxes is introduced at the interface between particles belonging to different phases. Specifically, the scheme adopted in the present work is an extension of the one described in [16] where the ALE formulation presented in [26] has been added. In particular, at the fluid interface the purely Lagrangian form of the ALE equations 5 is adopted for a strip of particles spanning a kernel radius. Readers can find also more information on general weakly-compressible SPH multiphase models in *e.g.* [15, 14, 12].

4 Preliminary test on a flat panel

In this section the results of the 2D single-phase simulations are described and compared to the experimental data from a wet drop test performed with a flat panel (panel length L equal to 64 cm, see Section 2) impacting with an angle of 4° and a vertical impact velocity U of 6.0 m/s.

As described in the theoretical work by [33], for this small angle a very thin, high-speed jet of water is formed, and the time-spatial gradients of the pressure field are extremely high. This makes the test conditions very demanding for numerical solvers. From the potential flow theory by [33], the jet thickness at model scale is about 0.1 mm. It is worth noting that the theory in [33] is formulated for symmetric wedge impacts whereas in the present case the

impact of a inclined single plate is considered. More details about the reference solution to be adopted are given in section 4.2.

On the base of this theoretical data, the 2D simulation has been conducted using a very high spatial resolution, corresponding to a particle size $\Delta x = 15.6\mu\text{m}$; by referring the latter to the panel length L , the ratio $L/\Delta x$ is equal to 41,000. The whole tank depth and width are, respectively, 3 m and 6 m. In order to manage such a small particle size a multi-resolution technique has been used. Specifically, the particle size gradually changes with a maximum magnification factor of 3,200 between the most refined region and the lowest resolution one (see figure 4). The total number of particles is about 3 million.

For small dead-rise angles water compressibility cannot be neglected when calculating the speed of the water jet U_{jet} (see e.g. [20, 7, 9]). In the experimental conditions the speed of sound in water is $c_0^* = 1481 \text{ m/s} \simeq 247 U$, therefore the Mach number $\text{Ma} = U/c_0^*$ is about 4×10^{-3} . Under such a condition an estimate of the jet speed is $U_{jet} \sim 42U \sim 250\text{m/s}$. As noted in [20], this very thin, high-speed jet disintegrates at some distance from the root due to interaction with both the surrounding air and the surface of the body. Note that in such kind of instability surface tension plays an important role on the jet evolution. This local and complex physics is not taken into account in the present numerical method but it is not supposed to play a relevant role on the pressure distribution.

Fig. 4. Flat panel impacting water. Colors are representative of the SPH velocity intensity. Pressure probe number 12, which is the gauge used for the comparison with the experimental data, is also depicted.

4.1 Selection of the speed of sound for the SPH model

Before starting the SPH simulations the speed of sound needs to be specified. As mentioned in section 3, the numerical Mach number usually adopted within the SPH simulations is $Ma = U/c_0 = 0.1$, which guarantees the weakly-compressible regime (i.e., compressibility plays a negligible role). Nonetheless, for this kind of impact the reference speed for the Mach number can not be the impact velocity U . Indeed, considering that the intersection point between the horizontal undisturbed free-surface and the wedge surface has a speed equal to $U_{inters} = U/\sin(\alpha) \simeq 14U$. The water jet formed during the impact has a speed higher than U_{inters} . Therefore, if one chooses the speed of sound using the wedge speed U , i.e., $c_0 = 10U$, the jet would not form at all, its speed being in the supersonic regime. This is a clear example where the weakly-compressible rule $Ma \leq 0.1$ needs to be enforced in a proper way, considering the specific problem at hand.

In the present case the reference speed should be the water jet speed U_{jet} which, however, is an unknown of the problem. Using the theory in [20], the estimate $U_{jet} = 40U$ can be used. Note that, using the latter constraint, the speed of sound in water would result even higher than the real one, $c_0 = 400U$ versus $c_0^* = 247U$. This means that for the adopted model scale water compressibility effects are not negligible, at least inside the jet region. However, considering that in the jet zone the pressure is close to the ambient pressure, water compressibility effects should not play a relevant role on the local impact loads.

In order to satisfy the weakly-compressible assumption, at least in the impact region, the reference velocity used is $U_{ref} = \sqrt{P_{max}/\rho}$, where P_{max} is an unknown of the problem and needs to be estimated. Then, an ex-post facto verification of the SPH simulations is required. Using the Wagner theory (which is valid for small deadrise angles as far as the air presence is negligible) the maximum pressure predicted is:

$$P_{max} = \frac{1}{2} \rho U^2 \frac{\pi^2/4}{[\tan(\alpha)]^2} \stackrel{\alpha=4^\circ}{\simeq} 252 \rho U^2 \quad (6)$$

corresponding to about 91 bar in our experiment.

The water-hammer pressure for this impact is $\rho c_0^* U = 88$ bar which is the maximum pressure level that can be physically reached in the experiments. The P_{max} predicted by potential flow theory is higher than the acoustic pressure, and this is a further indication that water compressibility cannot be neglected for this problem. Thus, considering $P_{max} \sim 80$ bar, the reference velocity is $U_{ref} = \sqrt{P_{max}/\rho} \sim 15U$ which is smaller than $U_{jet} = 40U$.

Fig. 5. Flat panel impacting water: colors are representative of the SPH pressure field. Red solid line is the free surface extracted from [33].

Taking this into account, a good compromise for the SPH speed of sound can be obtained by adopting a reference velocity $U_{ref} = 10U$ which implies a speed of sound $c_0 = 100U$ (i.e., Mach number $Ma = U/c_0 = 0.01$). The resulting time step is equal to $\Delta t = 1.5 \Delta x / c_0 \simeq 0.04 \mu s$ which is 250 times smaller than the sampling rate of the pressure probes used in the experiments (i.e., the SPH sample frequency is 25 MHz versus the 100 kHz of the experimental pressure probes). This aspect is expected to influence the observed pressure peak which, for the considered configuration, needs a high time/space resolution to be captured. Further, in order to verify the appropriateness of such a choice, also a simulation using $c_0^* = 247U$ has been run, the results will be shown at the end of section 4.2.

4.2 Comparison between SPH results, analytical solution and experimental data

Figure 5 shows the pressure field predicted by the SPH for the flat panel impact. In the same plot the free surface deformation evaluated by the potential flow theory by [33] is reported. Left plot of figure 6 shows an enlarged view of the flow velocity predicted by the SPH in the area of the highest pressure levels. A thin water jet is formed with a thickness of about 0.1 mm corresponding to about ten particles, thus justifying the high $L/\Delta x$ ratio needed to properly solve such a flow.

In the right plot of the same figure an enlarged view of the pressure field is shown (in this case the displayed pressure range is enlarged too). From this plot it is seen that the high-pressure region is limited to an area of 1 mm^2 with a pressure peak of about 60 bar. In the same figure the size of the probe used in the experiments is depicted. Clearly, the pressure sensor has a size much larger than the pressure bulb formed below the water-jet root. This aspect will be discussed in the following section.

Fig. 6. Flat panel impacting water: enlarged view of the impact zone. Left: contours of the velocity module. Right: contours of the SPH pressure field. The size of the pressure gauges used in the experiments is also depicted.

In figure 7 the time histories of the pressure measured at probe P_{12} are shown. This probe is positioned 23.6 cm from the left-hand edge of the panel (see figure 4). The SPH solution is compared with the experiments and with the pressure peak predicted by Wagner theory. The SPH prediction is between the two reference data sets, and is characterized by high-frequency components due to the fragmented jet of water that pass over the numerical pressure probe. The latter has a dimension of 0.125 mm (which is the size of the SPH kernel support) and the SPH sampling rate is 25 MHz. Both the SPH and the analytical predictions overestimate the experimental data for which the maximum pressure recorded is 34 bar (in the SPH solution the pressure peak reaches 70 bar whereas the analytical prediction is 91 bar). It has to be noted that, even though the Wagner theory is referred to the case of a symmetric wedge entry, the value of the pressure peak should substantially the same of the case of an oblique flat panel impact (see e.g. [13, 27]). Conversely, regarding the entire pressure signal, it is not possible to compare to classical analytical solutions, such as in [33], since they are all formulated for the symmetric wedge entry case.

As mentioned above, air entrainment is expected to play a minor role for deadrise angles greater than 3° [33, 27]. Notwithstanding that, most of the experimental measurements available in the literature for angles close to 4° exhibit pressure peaks much smaller than the one predicted by potential theory (cf., [11, 25, 27, 29]) and the values measured in the present study are in fair agreement with previous experiments by [27, 11]. As for possible 3D effects, these have been checked by comparing the pressure values on gauges aligned at the same distance from the piercing edge. For the probes positioned in the most central region no relevant differences have been observed. However, the maximum pressure impact measured in the experiment for small dead-rise angles can be also affected by:

- (1) Changes of the body velocity during the impact stage
- (2) Rotations of the body during the impact stage

Fig. 7. Flat panel impacting water: SPH pressure time histories at probe P_{12} compared with experimental data and with analytical solution Wagner theory.

Fig. 8. Flat panel impacting water: SPH pressure time histories versus experimental data. The SPH signal is filtered with a running average filters (MAF) at 100 kHz (dashed-dotted line).

- (3) Deformations of the wedge surface
- (4) Sampling rate of the pressure signals
- (5) Size of the pressure gauge

Thanks to the experimental setup adopted (see Section 2) the first three points can be neglected, while the last two can play an important role. In order to take into account the experimental sampling rate, the SPH signal has first been filtered using a moving average filter (MAF) reducing the numerical sampling rate from 25 MHz to 100 kHz. The result is illustrated in figure 8. The reduction of the SPH peak due to this filtering procedure is not enough to get a good agreement with the experimental data.

As a further step the SPH pressure has been measured integrating on a circular

Fig. 9. Flat panel impacting water: SPH pressure time histories versus experimental data . The SPH signal recorded using the size of the experimental pressure gauges and filtered at 100 kHz is also shown.

Fig. 10. Flat panel impacting water: experimental data for the pressure time histories on a row of probes (not equispaced). The time history from the first and last probes on the panel impacting the water are colored in red. The time history in blue is from probe P_{12} , used in the previous figures for comparison with the SPH solution.

area equal to the size of the experimental pressure probes and then filtered at 100 kHz. This result is shown in figure 9. In this case the SPH output is much closer to the pressure recorded in the experiment.

Summarizing, according to the analytical solution very narrow pressure peaks are expected for this kind of impact. Using pressure gauges with a size of few millimeters and a sampling rate of 100 kHz it is not possible to record such a localized event. Having in mind such limits, through SPH it is possible to get predictions close to the experimental data if the pressures are integrated over the experimental gauge area, even when using a speed of sound c_0 smaller than the real one c_0^* .

Fig. 11. Flat panel impacting water: SPH pressure time histories on a row of probes. The original SPH signals have been filtered with a MAF at 100 kHz as in the experimental signals. The time history from the first probe on the panel impacting the water is colored in red.

In figure 10 the experimental pressure time histories recorded on a sequence of pressure probes is reported. Even if the experimental pressure peaks present some fluctuations, very similar pressure evolutions are recorded with an almost constant time shift at each probe. The SPH results show quite good repeatability of the pressure peaks along the wedge surface as well (see figure 11). In this regard, it is worth comparing the propagation velocity of the pressure peak along the plate, U_P . Indeed, in water entry flows the value of the pressure peak should correlate to U_P^2 (see e.g. [17, 3]) as:

$$C_P = \frac{P_{max}}{1/2 \rho U_P^2} = 1. \quad (7)$$

In figure 12 the calculated values of U_P for both SPH and experimental results are reported for several probes. Only the probes far from the panel edges have been considered to avoid influences of either the initial impact stage or the final stage, for which the flow self-similarity is not applicable. In the same figure the values of U_P obtained from a simulation adopting the real speed of sound $c_0^* = 247U$ ($Ma=0.004$) are also reported. The difference between the simulation with $Ma=0.01$ and $Ma=0.004$ is very small (about 2% of the average value), confirming that within the weakly-compressible regime the Mach number effect is limited. For the sake of completeness in the same plot also the analytical value of U_P (valid for a wedge entry problem) is reported, i.e.:

$$U_P = \frac{\pi}{2} U \cot(\alpha). \quad (8)$$

In Table 1 The average values of U_P are reported. For the simulation at $Ma=0.01$ the average value of U_P is about 117 m/s corresponding to a pressure coefficient $C_P = 1.03$ which is close to the expected value (7). On the other

Fig. 12. Flat panel impacting water: Peak propagation velocity U_P calculated on several positions along the panel for the experiment (triangles), SPH simulation at $\text{Ma}=0.01$ (circles) and $\text{Ma}=0.004$ (squares), and analytical value from potential flow theory (dashed line). The origin of the x-axis is set at the left-hand edge of the panel.

	U_P (m/s)	$1/2\rho U_P^2$ (bar)	P_{max} (bar)	C_P
Exp.	104	54	30	0.56
SPH $\text{Ma}=0.01$	117	68	70	1.03
SPH $\text{Ma}=0.004$	119	71	75	1.06

Table 1

Average of the peak propagation velocity U_P plotted in fig. 12. The corresponding pressure peak $1/2\rho U_P^2$, the actual average pressure peak measured at the probes P_{max} and the related pressure coefficient C_P (7) are also reported.

hand since the value of U_P predicted by the SPH is smaller than the analytical one this implies that the maximum pressure of the SPH cannot be equal to the one predicted by the Wagner theory as shown above. This difference is essentially due to the fact that Wagner theory is referred to a symmetric wedge entry, while the present case is asymmetric (see section 4.3).

When considering the experimental pressure probes an average value of U_P equal to 104 m/s is obtained (with a standard deviation $\sigma = 3.1$). This propagation velocity of the pressure peak corresponds to a pressure coefficient C_P equal to 0.56. This confirms that the measurement system adopted is not able to record the real pressure peaks which are therefore underestimated as shown in this section.

4.3 Comparison between symmetric and asymmetric water entry

In the last subsection it has been shown that the pressure peak predicted by SPH is consistent with the water impact theory. Indeed, the calculated peak propagation velocity U_P and the pressure peak P_{max} give a pressure coefficient C_P close to unity (see eq. 7). Nonetheless, it still remains a significant discrepancy between SPH results and the analytical solution for this impact angle. In order to investigate the source of this incongruity a further simulation has been performed. As already mentioned, most of the analytical solutions available in the literature refer to a wedge entry problem. Therefore, the comparison between asymmetric (i.e. single flat panel entry) and symmetric (i.e. wedge entry) problem is useful to clarify the main cause behind the difference between SPH and analytical solutions.

The symmetric problem has been set by retaining the initial particle configuration of the asymmetric case and closing the fluid domain at the left edge of the panel with a vertical wall (see figure 13). The simulation has been run with $Ma=0.01$.

In figure 14 the peak propagation velocity for both symmetric and asymmetric problems are shown. It is clear that in the symmetric configuration the SPH solution is now much closer to the potential flow prediction, the computed average value being about 131 m/s (the theoretical value is 135 m/s). Because of this increase in the value of U_P , a larger pressure peak is expected on the panel surface. The recorded pressure at 0.16 m from the left-hand edge of the panel is shown in figure 15 for both symmetric and asymmetric SPH solutions.

Consistently with the observed value of U_P , the pressure peak of the symmetric solution is about 88 bar. In the same figures the analytical solutions from [31] and [33] are also reported. Evidently, the symmetric SPH solution is again much closer to the analytical prediction and the remaining difference can be

Fig. 13. Flat panel impacting water: fluid domain adopted in the symmetric problem configuration. Colors refer to the module of the velocity field.

mainly attributed to fluid compressibility. It is therefore clear that in the asymmetric problems the differences are not only limited to the pressure at stagnation (i.e. far from the pressure peak), which is expected to be lower due to the uprising jet at the left edge, but also the pressure peak intensity is affected (at least in the considered test conditions). This is in agreement with the analytical work in [28]. In that work it is shown that, generally, asymmetric impacts induce smaller pressure peaks with respect to the symmetric case. This effect is emphasized when the deadrise angle is smaller (in [28] the smallest angle considered is 10°).

Fig. 14. Flat panel impacting water: Peak propagation velocity U_P calculated on several positions along the panel for the asymmetric (circles) and symmetric (triangles) SPH simulations, and analytical value from potential flow theory (dashed line). The origin of the x-axis is set at the left-hand edge of the panel.

Fig. 15. Flat panel impacting water: pressure time histories of symmetric (solid line) and asymmetric (dashed) solutions measured at 0.16 m from the left-hand edge of the panel. Analytical solutions by [31] (dash-dot line) and by [33] (dash dot-dot line) are also reported.

5 Wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel

In the present section the results of the numerical simulations for the impact of the Mark III type insulation panel are described. The impact velocity U and the impact angle are again equal to 6.0 m/s and 4° , as for the case studied in the previous section. The geometry of the Mark-III insulation panel, used for wet drop test, was initially described by an Initial Graphics Exchange Specification (iges) file. The latter needed to be manipulated and transformed into an unstructured surface mesh in order to be a suitable input for the SPH code.

The geometrical impact configuration is given by the sketch in figure 16. The angle α has been set equal to 4° , this condition resulting as a critical one in the experiments. Some numerical pressure probes have been set in order to record pressure time histories during the simulation. The probe labels adopted for the experiments have been maintained in order to compare the numerical data with the reference one without any ambiguity.

Figure 17 shows bottom and lateral views of the numerical reconstruction of the Mark-III insulation panel along with the pressure probe positions. The present section is subdivided into three subsections addressing, respectively:

- i) 2D Simulation with a single-phase model
- ii) 3D Simulations with a single-phase model
- iii) 2D Simulation with a two-phase model.

5.1 2D Simulation with a single-phase model

The 2D profile of the corrugated panel has been extracted from central section of the panel. For this simulation a multi-resolution technique has been used in order to change the particle size with a magnification factor of 100 from the most refined region up to the lowest resolution one; the particle size

Fig. 16. Sketch of the impact configuration for the Mark-III insulation panel.

Fig. 17. Bottom and lateral views of the Mark-III insulation panel obtained using an unstructured mesh. On the left-hand plot labels for the pressure probes are shown.

Fig. 18. 2D single-phase model: particle-size distribution.

distribution is shown in figure 18. In the area involved in the impact, the spatial resolution is $\Delta x = 0.25\text{mm}$, the length L of the panel being 64 cm and the ratio $L/\Delta x$ being equal to 2560. Three different simulations with resolution ratios equal to $L/\Delta x = 640, 1280, 2560$ have been performed and figure 19 shows the pressure time histories at probe P_{40} recorded with the three different resolutions. The initial time $t = 0$ is set at the instant when the left dent touches the free-surface. The same rule has also been adopted for the following numerical test cases.

The plot depicted in figure 19 shows rather limited discrepancies for the

Fig. 19. 2D single-phase model: pressure-time evolution measured at probe P_{40} .

Fig. 20. 2D single-phase model: time evolution of the pressure field for six different time instants.

Fig. 21. 2D single-phase model: pressure time histories for six different probes. Comparison between experimental data and 2D single-phase SPH solution.

pressure peaks, hence for the present problem it is not necessary to reach the $L/\Delta x = 10,000$ used with the flat panel (see section 4.2) Thanks to this first analysis, we decided to use the ratio $L/\Delta x = 640$ for the 3D simulation (see the next section), and for conformity the results presented in this section will be compared with 3D ones using this spatial resolution.

Figure 20 depicts the pressure field during the impact stage. For this simulation the Mach number $\text{Ma} = U/c$ has been set equal to $\text{Ma} = 0.1$ since, as shown in the following, the pressure peaks are less intense relative to the ones recorded during the impact of the flat panel. At time $t = 6.5\text{ms}$ (first plot of figure 20) the left dent has completely entered in the fluid while the second one is only partially immersed. At this stage no relevant pressure peaks are observed.

The corresponding recorded pressure time histories are shown in figure 21 where the 2D single-phase SPH solution is compared to the experimental data for six different probes (the position of the probes is shown in the first plot of figure 20). At time $t = 9\text{ms}$ a pressure shock forms on the left part of the panel. From these first two pictures it is clear that a cavity is formed between the two dents and the free surface. Therefore, due to the absence of the air, this cavity is going to collapse inducing high pressure shocks (see time instants $t = 9\text{ms}$ and $t = 12\text{ms}$). This explains also the two consecutive peaks shown in figure 19: the first peak at $t = 11.5\text{ms}$ is due to the passage of the left jet propagating towards right; the second peak, at about $t = 12.5\text{ms}$, is due to the complete collapse of the cavity resulting from the encounter between the two jets.

As a consequence, in the time range $t = 11 - 14\text{ms}$ the maximum of the pressure is reached between probes P_{40} and P_{47} where peaks of 16 bar are measured. This pressure is linked to the water-hammer pressure $\rho c U_{cavity}$ where $U_{cavity} \simeq 27 \text{ m/s}$ is the relative velocity of the water fronts during the cavity collapse (an analogous impact has been described in [23] for the collapse of a plunging jet). The pressure calculated by the SPH model depends therefore by the specific speed of sound adopted (i.e. the specific Mach number used). However even adopting a Mach number of 0.1 the SPH pressure is four times higher than the pressure recorded in the experiments (4 bar versus 16 bar) and the experimental time history is much smoother resembling a sinusoidal function. This is a clear indication that air cushion effects cannot be neglected in the present problem.

The agreement between the numerics and the experimental data is better for probe P_{49} apart from for a slight delay of the SPH data. At time $t = 15\text{ms}$ a third pressure impact is recorded on the right-hand part of the panel reaching a pressure level of 8.5 bar at probe P_{53} where the experiments recorded a peak of 10.5 bar. In principle, in this region of the flow field, we do not expect relevant three-dimensional effects. Further, in this part of the panel air cushion effects

are not expected to be dominant and the flow resembles the one discussed for the flat panel (see Section 4). From figure 21 it is possible to observe that the duration of the peak registered at probe P_{53} is about 6 ms which is very close to the experimental one.

5.2 3D simulation with a single-phase model

After the 2D single-phase simulations a 3D simulation has been performed. Because of the large number of particles needed to accurately solve the water impact, a computing cluster has been used.

The computational resources needed to carry out the final 3D simulation were 300 cores running for about 180 hours. A resolution of $L/\Delta x = 640$ is used, as in the 2D simulations presented in the previous section, and also the Mach number has been kept equal to $Ma = 0.1$.

Figure 22 shows the fluid domain used in the simulation. The size of the domain has been chosen large enough to avoid any possible acoustic wave reflection within the selected time interval. As in the 2D cases a multi-resolution technique is used to get high spatial resolution only in the region of the water impact.

The pressure fields for three instants of time $t = 7.7, 12.7$ and 17.7 ms during the water impact are reported in figures 23 and 24. At time $t = 12.7$ ms the

Fig. 22. 3D single-phase model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: fluid domain used for the 3D simulation.

Fig. 23. 3D single-phase model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: planar and 3D views for two different time instants: 7.7, 12.7. The color contours are representative of the pressure fields. At time $t = 12.7$ ms a focusing effect is quite visible due to the closure of the entrapped cavity which induces a sudden rise of the pressure.

Fig. 24. 3D single-phase model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: planar and 3D views at time instant 17.7 ms. The color contours are representative of the pressure fields.

water jets entrapped in the cavity panel impact each other giving rise to a focusing effect. At this time the pressures reach values close to those calculated in the 2D simulations.

Figure 25 shows the time histories recorded by six different pressure probes: SPH 3D results are compared with experimental data. Similar to the 2D single-phase simulation (see previous section), the highest pressure levels are recorded at probes P_{40} and P_{47} . With respect to the 2D cases the highest pressure region has moved rightward from P_{40} toward probe P_{47} .

The impact pressure measured at probe P_{49} in the 3D simulation remains similar to the 2D case in terms of intensity while it occurs earlier, producing better agreement with the experiments.

As in the 2D case, large differences appear for probes P_{40} to P_{47} relative to the experimental measurements, confirming that these discrepancies are more likely related to air-cushion effects than to 3D effects.

Fig. 25. 3D single-phase model: pressure time histories for six different probes. Comparison between experimental data and 3D single-phase SPH solution.

5.3 2D simulation with a two-phase model

The numerical investigation described in this work is concluded by performing 2D simulations with air and water. The air is treated as a compressible gas using the classical polytropic state equation:

$$p = P_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_{0\,air}} \right)^{\gamma_{air}} \quad (9)$$

where $\rho_{0\,air}$ is the air density at rest, γ_{air} the air adiabatic index equal to 1.4, and P_0 the ambient pressure.

As opposed to the single-phase model, the speed of sound $c_{0\,air}$ cannot be adjusted for computational convenience as is for $c_{0\,water}$, since the former is directly linked with the Euler number used in the experiments ($Eu \simeq 17$):

$$\begin{aligned} Eu &= \frac{P_0}{\rho_{water} U^2}, \\ P_0 &= \frac{c_{0\,air}^2 \rho_{0\,air}}{\gamma_{air}}, \\ &\Downarrow \\ c_{0\,air} &= U \sqrt{Eu \gamma_{air} \left(\frac{\rho_{0\,water}}{\rho_{0\,air}} \right)} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, maintaining Eu number similitude and correctly simulating the air-cushion effects can result in quite high CPU costs, even in a 2D framework. We underline that with an Euler number of order 10 the air compressibility cannot be neglected, because density variations on the order of 10% are expected. This can represent a restriction for commercial software where air is treated as an incompressible medium, like the liquid phase. Moreover, Eu is of order 10 at model scale, while for full scale, it may reduce to order 1, thus further increasing the role of air compressibility. This latter aspect can be very important in the correct design of insulation panels.

The second point that makes the simulations with two phases more critical and complex with respect to the single phase model concerns the treatment of the fluid domain (reported in figure 26). The left-hand image shows the domain at the beginning of the simulation, while the right-hand image shows the configuration just before water impact. At this latter instant in time the intensity of the air velocity field is shown. Because of the complexity of the

Fig. 26. 2D two-phase model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: fluid domain used for the simulation.

air velocity field, we cannot start the simulation of the water impact ignoring it. On the other hand the domain depicted in the left-hand image of figure 26 is too large and it will incur significant CPU costs even in a 2D framework.

To avoid such a complexity the following strategy has been adopted: a first simulation from $t = 0.0$ to $t = 1.02\text{s}$ is performed considering the air-water interface as a solid boundary so only the air phase is simulated; at this stage the air can be treated as incompressible or weakly-compressible and a fictitious air speed of sound can be used in order to avoid too small time steps. Once the time $t = 1.02\text{s}$ is reached the air-water simulation is started using as input the air field from the previous simulation. In this second simulation the real air speed of sound is used and Eu number similitude is guaranteed. Figure 27 shows three time instants during the water impact stage.

In the left-hand column the air bubble entrapped by the panel is quite visible, while in the right-hand column the pressure contour levels are depicted. As for the previous simulations, the initial time for this case is set at the instant when the left dent touches the free-surface, that occurs 1.07 ms after the beginning of the air-water simulation. At $t = 5.23\text{ms}$ air cushioning effects occur and the air pressure starts rising. At $t = 8.33\text{ms}$ the pressure in the cavity is quite uniform with values of about 2 bar whereas a violent impact occurs at the left-hand corner of the panel.

At time $t = 11.03\text{ms}$ (see figure 28) an impact event is recorded close to the right-hand corner of the panel in the region around probe P_{53} , reaching a pressure level of 8 bar. At the same time the pressure in the panel cavity

Fig. 27. Two-phase 2D model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: views of liquid surface configuration (left) and pressure field (right) for time instants $t = -1.07\text{ms}$, $t = 5.23\text{ms}$ and $t = 8.33\text{ms}$.

remains uniform with levels of about 2.5 bar. At $t = 14.33\text{ms}$ the pressure field starts to decrease consequently to the air escaping under the right dent. This feature may also be responsible for the inhibition of the air pocket pressure oscillations, in a manner analogous to the air leakage effect observed in [1]. At the final instant depicted in figure 28, an almost uniform pressure of 1 bar acts on the panel surface.

In figure 29 the SPH pressure time histories for 6 different probes are compared with the experimental data. From this figure three relevant observations can be drawn:

- The two-phase SPH pressures inside the cavity panel, probes P_{37} to P_{47} , show a similar time behavior of the experimental pressure, thanks to the

Fig. 28. Two-phase 2D model, wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: views of liquid surface configuration (left) and pressure field (right) for time instants $t = 11.03\text{ms}$, $t = 14.33\text{ms}$ and $t = 19.13\text{ms}$.

correct simulation of the air-cushion phenomenon. However the two-phase SPH produces an underestimation of the pressure value (2.5 bar against 4 bar). This is an indication that in the experiments the air bubble is possibly smaller and more compressed.

- The SPH prediction of the pressure at probe P_{53} (close to the right-hand corner of the panel) is fair,
- All the numerical pressure peaks over-predict the time duration of the pressure impacts, which could be due to the 2D framework where the impact energy is more confined relative to the 3D one.

Fig. 29. 2D two-phase model: pressure time histories for six different probes: comparison between experimental data and 2D two-phase SPH solution.

Fig. 30. Wet drop test of Mark III type insulation panel: pressure time histories for probes P_{40} and P_{53} . Comparison among the different SPH simulations and the experimental data.

6 Perspective

From the analysis presented in this paper, the numerical simulations highlight the relevance of air-cushion effects when considering water impact of the Mark III type insulation panel with small impact angle. Thanks to the action of the air phase the pressure loads are drastically reduced with respect to those measured on a flat panel under the same impact conditions.

However, in our opinion, the present analysis needs to be extended to produce a more complete panorama of the problem. For example, if different impact angles are considered we expect that for larger angles air-cushion effects will not occur and significant loads would be experienced near the corrugation dents.

An analysis from a structural point of view could also be important. Indeed in the the work by [6] it is shown that the corrugation dents can be deformed during a violent wave impact event. Further, in this work we consider a simple wet-drop test. However, the final application shall be a wave impact against a wall covered with Mark III panels which represents a more interesting test from an engineering point of view. In fact, there are already some articles in the literature where preliminary investigations under these conditions are presented [see e.g. 5, 4].

In the present paper we stress the relevance of 3D effects together with air-cushioning. The main difficulties in tackling the problem including both of these aspects is linked to the high computational costs of the SPH solver. A further element to be considered in future is the influence of surface tension on peak duration. Incidentally, considering the ambient conditions inside an

LNG tank, the natural gas is close to its boiling temperature (see *e.g.* [2]) which makes the extension from model to full scale more complex [see *e.g.* 10].

7 Conclusions

In this work a numerical investigation of wet drop tests of insulation panels has been conducted. The numerical model adopted is the Riemann Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics model. Simulations have been conducted using 2D and 3D single phase models, whereas the air-water model simulations were only conducted in a 2D framework, because of the greater complexity and the high CPU costs needed to take air compressibility phenomena into account.

The water impact case studied is a 4° angle of impact, both flat and corrugated (Mark III type) insulation panel are considered. Because of the small angle of impact the selected test case is characterized by very high space-time gradients making the numerical simulations quite challenging.

For the flat panel only a 2D single-phase model has been used, since in the literature the air entrapment is said to play a minor role at this impact angle. Comparisons with theoretical and experimental data have been provided. The validation has regarded several parameters ranging from the free-surface deformation up to the consistency of the peak propagation velocity. A critical discussion addressing different key aspects of this simulation, such as the choice of the speed of sound and influence of the pressure measurement system, has been given.

For the Mark III type insulation panel, because of its geometrical form at 4° angle of impact both air cushioning and 3D effects can play relevant roles. To better investigate such aspects different simulations have been conducted. The comparisons reported in figure 30 summarize the results obtained at INSEAN; the two most critical probes, P_{40} (between the two dents) and P_{53} (close to the panel edge), are considered.

The most accurate comparisons have been obtained with the two-phase SPH model for both the probes (even for P_{53} where the air cushioning is not expected to be essential).

On the other hand all the 2D simulations present time scales too large with respect to the experiments. The 3D simulations, even with single phase, show the complexities of the impact for this geometry, different water jets are formed by the interaction between the free surface and the four dents of the panel.

Summarizing, a further investigation with a 3D two-phase model would allow

further inspection of the phenomenon, providing more accurate results in time-space pressure distribution. Further, a remarkable improvement of the solution could be provided by the addition of a surface tension model in order to simulate the multiple bubble break-up and, consequently, to achieve a more realistic evolution of the air cushioning.

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